

DISSOLVED OXYGEN IN RIVER WATERS QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS

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Annotation. Taking into account the sources of oxygen supply to reservoirs during the organization of water self-purification processes is the basis of various processes occurring in reservoirs, and the search for solutions to questions about whether this matters when water leaves reservoirs is shown in the article..

Keywords: oxygen, pressure, process, reservoir, molecules

Within the framework of this article, in the conditions of our republic, the level of self-purification of river waters may vary depending on the level of oxygen in river waters and air in the atmosphere.

The volume content of oxygen in the atmosphere is mainly 21%. In the air at a time when its weight is 1.43 g/l, the oxygen density is 0.3 g/l. It is shown that the solubility of oxygen in water can have different values depending on the water temperature and oxygen pressure in the air compared with solutions of leakage of water sources, depending on Henry's law.

The concentration of oxygen in water in the dissolved state, its change over time and environmental conditions are an important part of the classification of water bodies as mobile in the ecosystem. The state of oxygen regimes in reservoirs largely depends on the internal processes occurring in reservoirs, and is associated with the dynamics of organic substances contained in the water.

Because in the external environment, during the primary collision of water – as a

result of photosynthesis-oxygen appears in it, and during pollution, during destruction, oxygen is lost from the composition of water.

Taking into account the sources of oxygen supply to reservoirs during the organization of water self-purification processes is the basis of various processes occurring in reservoirs, and is important when these waters leave reservoirs.

We can see how the processes of circulating movement of dissolved oxygen proceed on the basis of the scheme presented in Figure 1.

It can be seen from the diagram that water supply to reservoirs comes from water sources located near reservoirs – through Hammam systems as a result of synthesis in the atmosphere; while consumption can occur in Hammam systems of reservoirs by outflow, merging with the atmosphere, chemical oxidation of inorganic substances in water, destructive oxygen consumption through organic substances.

Oxygen is always present in the water of open reservoirs in a dissolved state. The presence of dissolved oxygen in water characterizes the oxygen regime of reservoirs and is an important factor determining the ecological and sanitary condition of reservoirs. It is important that oxygen is always present in the water in dissolved form and in sufficient quantity, since it is important for the respiration of hydrobionts contained in the water.

Oxygen is also involved in the process of self-purification of water, since it participates in the oxidation of various organic substances trapped in the water and in the decomposition of various dead organic substances contained in it. If the oxygen concentration in the water decreases, this indicates a change in biological processes in the reservoir, which means that the reservoir is contaminated with biochemically rapidly oxidizing substances (which in the first case were organic).

Figure -1. Scheme of dissolved oxygen circulation in reservoirs

Depletion of the oxygen content in water also occurs as a result of the oxidation of organic substances present in water, as well as as a result of existing chemical processes for the recovery of substances and respiration of aquatic organisms.

Saturation of reservoirs with oxygen occurs as a result of its interaction with air (absorption), as well as as a result of photosynthesis in algae, i.e. under the influence of physico-chemical and biochemical processes. In reservoirs, oxygen is supplied through rain and snow water. Consequently, the high or low oxygen content in water, as already mentioned, is influenced by various reasons. Dissolved oxygen is present in water as an O₂ molecule dissolved in water. The amount of dissolved oxygen depends on the ambient temperature, atmospheric pressure, turbulence of water movement, precipitation, the degree of mineralization of water and other factors.

Depending on the degree of heating of the water, the oxygen concentration in the water changes accordingly. It is possible to determine the amount of oxygen dissolved in water using special tables. We determine the degree of oxygen saturation of water in relation to the level of water heating, based on 100% of the size. The amount of oxygen in water increases with a decrease in water temperature and degree of mineralization, as well as with an increase in atmospheric pressure.

In open reservoirs, the dissolved oxygen content in water ranges from 0 to 14 mg / l, and its amount will also depend on the season and daily fluctuations. In waters with degraded water quality and a high level of organic pollution, there will be a shortage of oxygen. A decrease in the oxygen content in water by 2 mg / l, leads to the mass extinction of fish and other aquatic organisms living in it.

In reservoirs, the content of dissolved oxygen in water for at least 12 hours a day at all intervals of the year should not exceed 4 mg/ l –MPC, and for fish farms -6 mg / l in summer and 4 mg / l in winter.

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